

MALICIOUS URL DETECTION USING MACHINE LEARNING

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ABSTRACT

The simplest approach to get sensitive information from unwitting people is through a phishing attack. The goal of phishers is to obtain crucial data, such as username, password, and bank account information. People working in cyber security are currently looking for reliable and consistent methods of detecting phishing websites. In order to distinguish between legal and phishing URLs, this article uses machine learning technology. It extracts and analyses many aspects of both types of URLs.

Algorithms such as Support Vector Machine, Decision Tree, and Random Forest are used to identify phishing websites. The paper's objective is to identify phishing URLs and identify the best machine learning method by evaluating each algorithm's accuracy rate, false positive rate, and false negative rate.

INTRODUCTION

Due of how simple it is to develop a phoney website that closely resembles a legitimate website, phishing is now a top worry for security researchers. Although experts can spot fraudulent websites, not all users can, and as a result, some users fall prey to phishing scams. The attacker's primary goal is to obtain login information for bank accounts. Businesses in the United States lose \$2 billion annually as a result of their customers falling for phishing scams. According to the third Microsoft Computing Safer Index Report, which was published in February 2014, the yearly global cost of phishing might reach \$5 billion. Because users are not aware of phishing assaults, they are becoming more successful. It is highly challenging to combat phishing attacks since they prey on user vulnerabilities, yet it is crucial to improve phishing detection methods. The "blacklist" method, which is the standard technique for detecting phishing websites, involves adding blacklisted URLs and Internet Protocol (IP) addresses to the antivirus database. Attackers modify

the URL to appear authentic by obfuscation and many other straightforward ways, such as fast-flux, in which proxies are automatically constructed to host the website, algorithmic production of new URLs, etc., to dodge blacklists. This method's primary flaw is its inability to identify zero-hour phishing attacks.

Heuristic-based detection, which takes into account traits that have been observed to exist in actual phishing attacks, is capable of spotting zero hour phishing attacks. However, the traits are not always guaranteed to be present in such attacks, and the false positive rate for detection is very high.

PROJECT OVERVIEW

To acquire user information, scammers employ a variety of techniques, including email, Uniform Resource Locators (URL), instant messaging, calls, and text messages.

The suggested model's main goal is to identify phishing attacks by examining the attributes of phishing websites and the blacklist database. Our proposal is limited to aspects of domain names and URLs. We used JavaScript PL when creating this functionality. Blacklisting and semantic analysis techniques were combined to be able to recognise and stop the phishing attack.

EXISTING SYSTEM

A current system scans the research on phishing attack detection. Phishing attacks target holes in systems that exist because of the involvement of humans. Users are the weakest link in the security chain since a large majority of cyberattacks are disseminated using techniques that take use of vulnerabilities detected in end users. Since there is no single, effective way to address all of the weaknesses in phishing, numerous strategies are frequently used to counteract particular attacks. Many of the recently used phishing mitigation strategies are surveyed in this study. We believe it is important to highlight where the phishing detection strategies belong in the whole mitigation process, thus a high-level overview of the several categories of phishing mitigation approaches, such as detection, offensive defence, rectification, and prevention, is also offered.

DISADVANTAGES

- 1) The system is less effective because it is not used for many datasets.
- 2) The system does not use data preprocessing, and the number of classifiers is not evaluated.

PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system creates the notions listed below, which IP address in URL: If an IP address is included in the URL, the feature is set to 1, otherwise it is set to 0. The majority of trustworthy websites never use an IP address as the URL to download a webpage. The use of an IP address in a URL suggests that the attacker is attempting to steal sensitive data.

@ symbol in the URL: If the @ symbol is present in the URL, the feature is set to 1; otherwise, it is set to 0. When phishers add a specific @ sign to a URL, the browser ignores everything before the "@" symbol and frequently skips over the true address that usually comes after.

Hostname dot count: Phishing URLs frequently include a lot of dots in them. For instance, in the URL <http://shop.fun.amazon.phishing.com>, the word "amazon" is used to deceive users into clicking on it even though phishing.com is a real domain name. The typical number of dots in safe URLs is 3. The feature is set to 1 if there are more than 3 dots in the URLs; otherwise, it is set to 0.

Prefix or suffix separated from the domain name by the dash (-) symbol: If the feature is set to 1 for the domain name, otherwise it is set to 0. Rarely used, the dash symbol (-) is added to the domain name to give users the impression that they are visiting a trustworthy website.

Email information submission: The "mailto:" or "mailto:" functionalities could be used by the phisher to direct the user's data to his personal email. If the URL contains such functions, feature is set to 1; otherwise, it is set to 0.

ADVANTAGES

Proposes a Decision Tree Algorithm which implements for Presence of sensitive words in URL.

The proposed system incorporates which Phishes can make a use of Unicode characters in URL to trick users to click on it.

MODULES

SERVICE PROVIDER

In this module, the Service Provider has to login by using valid user name and password. After login successful he can do some operations, such as Browse Website URLs and Train & Test Data Sets, View Trained and Tested Accuracy in Bar Chart, View Trained and Tested Accuracy Results, View Prediction Of Website URL Type, View Website URL Type Ratio, Download Trained Data Sets, View Website URL Type Ratio Results, View All Remote Users.

VIEW AND AUTHORIZE USERS

In this module, the admin can view the list of users who all registered. In this, the admin can view the user's details such as, user name, email, address and admin authorize the users.

REMOTE USER

In this module, there are n numbers of users are present. User should register before doing any operations. Once user registers, their details will be stored to the database. After registration successful, he has to login by using authorized user name and password. Once Login is successful user will do some operations like predict website URL type, view your profile.

RESULTS

Fig: User Output

Fig: Confusion Matrix

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This paper aims to enhance detection method to detect phishing websites using machine learning technology. We achieved 97.14% detection accuracy using random forest algorithm with lowest false positive rate. Also result shows that classifiers give better performance when we used more data as training data. In future hybrid technology will be implemented to detect phishing websites more accurately, for which random forest algorithm of machine learning technology and blacklist method will be used.

In future if we get structured dataset of phishing, we can perform phishing detection much faster than any other technique. In future we can use a combination of any other two or more classifier to get maximum accuracy. We also plan to explore various phishing techniques that uses Lexical features, Network based features, Content based features, Webpage based features and HTML and JavaScript features of web pages which can improve the performance of the system. In particular, we extract features from URLs and pass it through the various classifiers.

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